

Deliverable 2.7

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES, 36-
INSA

Contributing partners: 25-NUIG

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7 (Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7))		
WP and task	WP2, JRP15-R2-WP2-T7		
Leader	2-AGES, 36-INSA		
Other contributors	25-NUIG		
Due month of the deliverable	M36		
Actual submission month	M60		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 14.12.2022		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>	EEA <input type="checkbox"/>
	EMA <input type="checkbox"/>	FAO <input type="checkbox"/>	WHO <input type="checkbox"/>
	OIE <input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other international stakeholder(s):		
	Social Media:		

	<u>Other recipient(s):</u>
--	----------------------------------

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7

I. Introduction

1. Description of the task JRP15-R2-WP2-T2.7

In task JRP15-R2-**WP2-T7** (*Isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments. Sequence comparisons.*)

We used the extracted extracellular free DNA from all the collected samples the samples according to the generated protocols based on previous literature available. We performed gene enrichment as described in WP2-T3.

2. Deliverable description

In this deliverable (*Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7)*) we first evaluated the quality of the extracted total and extracellular free DNA with fluorometry. Qubit measurements of double stranded DNA were done for all the samples and concentrations expressed in ng/μL. In general, concentrations were below 10ng/μL for exDNA and above 10 ng/μL for total DNA. Further quality assessments of the samples were done as explained in D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6. In addition, we removed from the analysis all those genes with a coverage below 0.5. For a total of 475 samples 7252 different antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) were detected.

Most samples presented good amount of Transcripts Per Kilobase Million (TPMs). Only 21 out of 475 had an insufficient number of reads. In figure 1 the TPMs in the samples by country and DNA type can be seen. Overall, the number of TPMs for the exDNA was similar to that of the total DNA:

The ARGs with the highest TPM sums corresponded to the tetracycline ARG *tetW*, which was present in 343 samples, and mutations in ribosomal subunits:

	Marker ID	Cluster ID	Marker	length marker	ARE5db	name ARE5db marker class
AR012494	"AR012494_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1454"	"rrsB"		"16S_rRNA"
AR012489	"AR012489_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1551"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012487	"AR012487_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1441"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012196	"AR012196_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR009379	"AR009379_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012520	"AR012520_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3103"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012496	"AR012496_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1504"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012187	"AR012187_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012492	"AR012492_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1542"	"rrsC"		"16S_rRNA"
AR014249	"AR014249_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3138"	"rrl"		"16S_rRNA"
AR012190	"AR012190_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014258	"AR014258_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2923"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012191	"AR012191_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014242	"AR014242_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1584"	"rrs"		"16S_rRNA"
AR012484	"AR012484_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1537"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012485	"AR012485_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1544"	"rrsD"		"16S_rRNA"
AR015255	"AR015255_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1529"	"rrsA"		"16S_rRNA"
AR012523	"AR012523_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2904"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012506	"AR012506_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2926"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012511	"AR012511_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2904"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR015246	"AR015246_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1543"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012522	"AR012522_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2904"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR009381	"AR009381_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR009378	"AR009378_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012203	"AR012203_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012200	"AR012200_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012497	"AR012497_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1528"	"rrsB"		"16S_rRNA"
AR009379	"AR009379_2"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014252	"AR014252_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1545"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012194	"AR012194_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014253	"AR014253_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2899"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012490	"AR012490_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1544"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012519	"AR012519_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3112"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR014256	"AR014256_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2905"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012185	"AR012185_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014240	"AR014240_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2904"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR014179	"AR014179_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1889"	"Tet(O/W)"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012193	"AR012193_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012498	"AR012498_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1486"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012186	"AR012186_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR015285	"AR015285_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2910"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012201	"AR012201_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012501	"AR012501_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2900"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012517	"AR012517_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3112"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012199	"AR012199_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012486	"AR012486_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1551"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012204	"AR012204_2"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014180	"AR014180_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1889"	"Tet(O/W)"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012505	"AR012505_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3113"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012514	"AR012514_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3135"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012483	"AR012483_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1542"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR014257	"AR014257_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1544"	"rrsD"		"16S_rRNA"
AR009380	"AR009380_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014181	"AR014181_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1889"	"Tet(O/W)"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR009380	"AR009380_2"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014182	"AR014182_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1889"	"Tet(O/W)"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012516	"AR012516_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3112"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR014254	"AR014254_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2898"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR009382	"AR009382_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tet(W_N_W)"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014255	"AR014255_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2898"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012518	"AR012518_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3112"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012521	"AR012521_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3118"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR015249	"AR015249_1"	"AR012505_1"	"2905"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012524	"AR012524_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3149"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012195	"AR012195_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012512	"AR012512_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3135"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012513	"AR012513_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3135"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012515	"AR012515_1"	"AR012505_1"	"3162"	"23S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR012197	"AR012197_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR014183	"AR014183_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1889"	"Tet(O/W)"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR012500	"AR012500_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1542"	"rrsH"		"16S_rRNA"
AR012204	"AR012204_1"	"AR012194_1"	"1920"	"tetW"		"tetracycline_resistance_ribosomal_protection_protein"
AR015245	"AR015245_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1543"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"
AR015247	"AR015247_1"	"AR012497_1"	"1536"	"16S_rRNA"		"mutation_or_variant_antibiotic_target"

As for the number of ARGs in each compartment, there was variations among compartments, DNA type and countries:

After this overview on ARGs quantity and diversity we are conducting more complex statistical analyses to fully understand the differences between compartments, countries and DNA types regarding ARGs, their antibiotic class and resistance mechanism.